

CONCEPT OF WILL AND ITS THEORIES

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Abstract. This article presents the recommendations of scientific studies about the concept of will and its theories. Also, in the article, the scientific proposal and practical recommendations formed by the author on this issue were also expressed.

Keywords. Will, behavior, voluntarism, subject, need, inclinations, motivational, regulatory, hierarchy.

Introduction. Summarizing the definitions of will in psychology, it can be described in the following way: "Will is a person's conscious organization of activities, behavior and behavior aimed at overcoming the difficulties encountered in the process of achieving the goals, changes means input and self-management. Will is a specific form of individual activity, behavior, organization of the subject's behavior determined by the goal set by him. The will appears in work, play, study, behavior, behavior of a person who acquires the laws of nature, society, and personal development and thus has the opportunity to master them according to his needs."

According to the interpretation of psychological data, the will ensures the performance of two interrelated tasks - stimulating and inhibiting functions, and manifests itself in their creation.

The main part. Will means desire, desire, goal in Arabic. It is the ability of a person to consciously direct his actions (in activity, behavior, behavior) towards the realization of a certain goal, to be persistent in this way, to overcome existing obstacles. is a psychological ability. Will is an important feature of human activity, behavior and behavior, an important factor that determines the content of his life. Consistency of activity and behavior is observed in a strong-willed person. The feeling of confidence in achieving the goal set before the person is the strength of the will and the main criterion. After all, strong faith creates a basis for overcoming difficulties on the way to the goal, both physically and mentally. Due to the existence of different teachings in the sciences of philosophy and psychology, they also interpret the will as pertaining to God and the individual. For the same reason, the words and concepts of God's will and the servant's will were created. In some teachings, God's will is described as a force that determines the specific norm and balance of the laws of nature and social development. However, the development of each society, the implementation of its advanced ideas in marriage is realized in many ways depending on the will of the members of this society. From a scientific, philosophical and psychological point of view, our ancestors have long paid great attention to the formation of the will of the people and the nation. Faith and will are always described in harmony. Because these two concepts are the ideological and spiritual basis of certain views and teachings. It is known that faith's weakness or strength,

compatibility (proportion) or incompatibility (disproportion) with universal and national interests also play an important role in the formation of strong, thorough and strong will.

In the sciences of philosophy and psychology, the concept of "free will" is used in most cases. Freedom of will is a person's conscious desire to do something. During the socio-historical development in philosophy and psychology, there is a debate about the definition of free will, between secular and religious doctrines on this basis. For example, representatives of fatalism emphasize that all actions of a person are determined only by external forces, while representatives of the theory of voluntarism advance the conclusive view that human behavior is absolutely free, and such freedom does not depend on external forces in any way. they push In religious teachings, it is said that God determines the will in general, including free will, and the fate and destiny of a person depends on the will of the Creator, it is predetermined. Also, there is a different interpretation in some religious teachings, in which the idea that a person has free will and is responsible for his sins is put forward.

Will - the objective world reflected by the subject's internal conditions (needs, interests, wishes, desires, inclinations, knowledge, etc.) creates opportunities for him to set various goals, make decisions, and freely act. . On reflection, not a will that is chosen according to one's desires, but a will that is adequately sorted according to objective necessity is free.

Approaches, mechanisms, involuntary (unconscious) and voluntary (conscious) behavior, decision-making forms, characteristics related to the category of will, based on the laws created in the science of psychology, relying on the essence of theories, concepts, such as motivational, regulatory, time freedom; the role of volitional qualities in the formation of personality; the uniqueness of the function of will in ensuring the success of activity, behavior, behavior; the teachings of our great ancestors about the will, for example, the observation of the significance of the teachings of Sufism in the formation of the will; theory of perfect man; Ideas about a perfect personality in the works of President Islam Karimov; documents of our state "National Program of Personnel Training", "Law" on education; The fact that the concept of "I" is the possibility of self-expression and management (regulation) serves as the methodology and research basis of this monograph.

Also, a new approach to the will as a multifunctional category in psychology, the essence of the original concept has been clarified; that the description of the internal and external factors of the will formation process has been created; specific comments and observations regarding the structure (hierarchy) of the will; The analysis of approaches to will is summarized according to certain signs and symptoms; pathological states of the will are explained on the basis of experimental materials; interpretation of gender relations and aspects of will formation; It has been proved that the forms of the psyche (activity, character, behavior) are a unique influencing and driving force in the formation of the will; the comparative analysis of the role of environmental, internal and external factors in the process of formation, etc., is a scientific and theoretical novelty of this monograph.

The main factor in the emergence of will is the systematic implementation of activity structures and volitional actions by a person, and the activity of a person who embodies and harmonizes with consciousness in such actions. Volitional activity requires mental-intellectual actions that are practical and require voluntary effort to implement mental processes that are deeply understood, mastered, and mastered by a person on a large scale. Such mental-intellectual, creative (creative) actions are assessment of the emergency situation, selection of

means, methods, operations for actions intended for implementation in the future, selection of pedagogical-psychological guidelines for aiming and achieving it, among them for use, such as making a certain decision, execution. In our opinion, it is appropriate to consider all mental, creative, factor actions as the operational, technological side of volitional activity.

Summary. Based on the above considerations, it is impossible to assess and recognize the level of research of will as a scientific category in modern psychology as satisfactory, because if there is no person with a strong will to fulfill the tasks set before the citizens by the society, they will not be able to afford it. In our opinion, the development of science and technology, the expansion of the information system, and the improvement of the economic system require the formation of a strong-willed, creative thinker and well-rounded person. Because modern young people realize the possibilities of acquiring knowledge and expanding their spirituality with the help of interactive methods, they form the qualities of responsibility, self-sacrifice, patriotism, creativity, discipline, fortitude, and patience.

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